

RESPONSE OF SEGMENTED-STIFFNESS COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

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SUMMARY: The paper examines the displacement response of round cylinders constructed in such a fashion that the crown and keel are made of one pseudo-isotropic laminate and the sides are made of another pseudo-isotropic laminate. The terminology segmented-stiffness is given to this construction. Considered is the displacement response for two loading conditions: 1 - compressive axial strain, or; 2) internal pressure but with the restraint that the overall axial strain is zero. Infinite-length and finite-length cylinders are studied, the former for pedagogical reasons. The distinguishing characteristic of this construction is the presence of a circumferential displacement. For the finite-length case, in addition to the existence of a circumferential displacement, the radial displacement varies with circumferential location. For the axial strain condition the primary parameter responsible for these characteristics is the mismatch in the effective Poisson's ratios between the segments, while for the pressure loading condition, the mismatch between extensional moduli of the segments is responsible. The inplane shear moduli have much less influence on the problem.

KEYWORDS: internal pressure, compressive axial strain, nonaxisymmetric response

INTRODUCTION

Composite fuselage structures may well be made in such a way that the laminate stacking sequence varies with circumferential location around the fuselage. The stacking sequence at the top and bottom of the fuselage may be axially stiff to resist axial tensile and compressive loads due to fuselage bending, while the sides may be designed to resist shear loading. This variation in stacking sequence could well be continuous, with the stacking sequence at the top and bottom making a smooth transition to another stacking sequence at the sides. As an alternative, there could be discrete changes in laminate stacking sequence at specific locations around the fuselage circumference. This would allow the fuselage to be manufactured in circumferential sections, a manufacturing convenience, but would result in a stepwise change in laminate properties at circumferential locations where the different laminates join. Figure 1 illustrates a fuselage cross section with the crown, side, and keel fabricated of different laminates. The crown and the keel segments subtend angles $2\theta_c$ and $2\theta_k$, respectively. In reality, there may even be a stiff beam forming the backbone of the keel, and there may be stiffeners at other circumferential locations. For the present work, stiffeners will not be considered and as a result of the discrete change in stiffness, rather unusual response might be expected. In particu-

lar, the response of the fuselage to even simple axisymmetric loads such as compressive axial strain or internal pressure could result in variations in the radial, axial, and circumferential displacements with respect to circumferential location. These displacement gradients in the circumferential direction could, in turn, lead to unfavorable stress fields where the segments join. Though ultimate interest could well focus on the construction of fig. 1, the study here will focus on a simpler situation, namely one where the crown and keel laminates are identical and subtend the same arc length, $2\theta^*$. Additionally, it will be assumed that all laminates are balanced and symmetric and D_{16} and D_{26} are zero. Thus, with compressive axial strain or internal pressure, the problem exhibits quarter symmetry.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

A first-order shear-deformable theory [1] will be used to study the response of a clamped quarter-cylinder of radius R and length L , the nomenclature of the problem being shown in fig. 2. The axial coordinate is x and the arc-length coordinate is s , where s^* , which is equal to $R\theta^*$, denotes the coordinate where the segments join. The displacements of the cylinder's reference surface in the axial, circumferential, and radial directions are u , v , and w , respectively, and they are assumed to be of the form

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, s, z) &= u(x, s) + z \cdot \psi_x(x, s) \\ v(x, s, z) &= v(x, s) + z \cdot \psi_s(x, s) \\ w(x, s, z) &= w(x, s) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the nomenclature is standard for a first-order shear-deformable theory and z is the wall-thickness coordinate measured outward from the reference surface (midwall) location. As a result of the above kinematic assumptions, the reference surface strains and curvatures, and the force and moment resultants, have the following forms

Fig. 1 - Crown-side-keel arrangement for a circular fuselage

Fig. 2 - Problem nomenclature

$$\begin{aligned}
\varepsilon_x &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \gamma_{xs} &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial s} & \varepsilon_s &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial s} + \frac{w}{R} \\
\gamma_{rs} &= \psi_s + \frac{\partial w}{\partial s} & \gamma_{rx} &= \psi_x + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\
\kappa_x &= \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial x} & \kappa_s &= \frac{\partial \psi_s}{\partial s} & \kappa_{xs} &= \frac{\partial \psi_s}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial s}
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
N_x &= A_{11}\varepsilon_x + A_{12}\varepsilon_s & N_s &= A_{12}\varepsilon_x + A_{22}\varepsilon_s & N_{xs} &= A_{66}\gamma_{xs} \\
Q_s &= A_{44}\gamma_{rs} & Q_x &= A_{55}\gamma_{rx} \\
M_x &= D_{11}\kappa_x + D_{12}\kappa_s & M_s &= D_{12}\kappa_x + D_{22}\kappa_s & M_{xs} &= D_{66}\kappa_{xs}
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The material stiffnesses A_{11}, \dots, D_{66} have the usual meaning [2, 3]. It is important to realize that there is a set of material stiffnesses for the crown and keel of the cylinder and a set for the sides. Quantities associated with the crown (and keel) and sides will be denoted with a ‘c’ or ‘s,’ respectively.

The geometrically linear form of the equations that govern equilibrium of circular cylindrical shells for this shear-deformable theory are

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_{xs}}{\partial s} &= 0 & \frac{\partial N_s}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial N_{xs}}{\partial x} &= 0 & \frac{\partial Q_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q_s}{\partial s} - \frac{N_s}{R} + q_o &= 0 \\
\frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial M_{xs}}{\partial s} - Q_x &= 0 & \frac{\partial M_s}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial M_{xs}}{\partial x} - Q_s &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where q_o is the internal pressure. The boundary conditions at the ends of the clamped cylinder, $x = \pm L/2$, are,

$$v = w = \psi_x = \psi_s = 0 \tag{5}$$

For the axial strain condition the u displacements at the ends impress a known average axial strain $\bar{\varepsilon}_x$. For the pressure loading condition $u=0$ on the ends. The quarter symmetry assumption requires the following boundary conditions at $s = 0$ and $\pi R/2$:

$$N_{xs} = v = Q_s = M_{xs} = \psi_s = 0 \tag{6}$$

In order to isolate the material properties which are most significant in the interaction between the crown and side sections, in this study each section is assumed to be constructed of a pseudo-isotropic laminate. Accordingly, the effective inplane engineering properties of each section are: the extensional modulus, E ; Poisson’s ratio, ν ; and the shear modulus, G . Though in each segment the properties are the same in all directions, E , ν , and G are independent of each other. The effective engineering properties chosen are from the cases listed in Table 1. The properties of the side are assigned as the baseline and the material properties of the crown are varied. Note that for each case of crown properties only one of the effective properties is varied (the one underlined) and it is taken to be 1.5 times the baseline property.

Table 1: Effective engineering properties used to study segmented-stiffness cylinders.

		E (GPa)	ν	G (GPa)
Side (baseline)		70	0.2	30
Crown	Case 1	<u>105</u>	0.2	30
	Case 2	70	<u>0.3</u>	30
	Case 3	70	0.2	<u>45</u>

INFINITE- LENGTH CYLINDER

It is instructive to consider the case of an infinitely long cylinder with a quarter-symmetric cross section subjected to known axial strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x$, which is assumed to be independent of x and s , or an internal pressure. For either of these loading conditions, and for the class of laminates considered, v , w , and ψ_s are independent of x and ψ_x is zero. The equations of equilibrium, eq. 4, become ordinary differential equations in the arc-length coordinate s and they can be integrated directly. The boundary conditions of eq. 6 at $s = 0$ and $s = \pi R/2$ and enforcement of continuity of v , w , ψ_s , N_s , M_s , and Q_s at $s = s^*$ provide conditions for solving for the constants of integration. The final result indicates ψ_s is zero and for the axial strain condition the radial displacement is given by

$$w^c = w^s = -\left(\frac{A_{12}^s}{A_{22}^s} \left(\frac{\pi R - 2s^*}{\pi R}\right) + \frac{A_{12}^c}{A_{22}^c} \frac{2s^*}{\pi R}\right) R \bar{\epsilon}_x \quad (7)$$

while the circumferential displacement is given by the expressions

$$v^c(s) = \frac{(A_{12}^s A_{22}^c - A_{12}^c A_{22}^s) \bar{\epsilon}_x (\pi R - 2s^*) s}{A_{22}^s A_{22}^c \pi R}, \quad 0 \leq s \leq s^* \quad (8)$$

$$v^s(s) = \frac{(A_{12}^s A_{22}^c - A_{12}^c A_{22}^s) \bar{\epsilon}_x (\pi R - 2s) s^*}{A_{22}^s A_{22}^c \pi R}, \quad s^* \leq s \leq \pi R/2 \quad (9)$$

For the internal pressure condition, which, recall, is axially restrained,

$$w^c(s) = w^s(s) = \frac{2q_o R}{\pi} \left[\frac{s^*}{A_{22}^c} + \frac{(\pi R/2 - s^*)}{A_{22}^s} \right] \quad (10)$$

$$v^c(s) = \frac{2q_o}{\pi} \frac{(A_{22}^s - A_{22}^c)}{A_{22}^c A_{22}^s} \left(\frac{\pi R}{2} - s^*\right) s, \quad 0 \leq s \leq s^* \quad (11)$$

$$v^s(s) = \frac{2q_o}{\pi} \frac{(A_{22}^s - A_{22}^c)}{A_{22}^c A_{22}^s} \left(\frac{\pi R}{2} - s \right) s^*, \quad s^* \leq s \leq \pi R/2 \quad (12)$$

These are exact solutions and it is seen by eqs. 7 and 10 that for both loading conditions the radial displacement w is independent of s , meaning the circular cylinder deforms radially into another circle with a slightly different radius. Furthermore, for both cases the circumferential displacement v is a bilinear function of s , reaching a maximum magnitude at $s=s^*$. This non-zero circumferential displacement is in contrast to the lack of any circumferential displacement for the case of a cylinder constructed of a single laminate. This nonzero circumferential displacement is similar to the response of an elliptical cylinder (isotropic or composite) to internal pressure[4]. With an elliptical cylinder the lack of axisymmetry comes from the geometry, while for the problem here the lack of axisymmetry is due to the variable material properties. It would appear that any deviation from the axisymmetric condition results in circumferential displacements. It can be shown that for effective pseudo-isotropic engineering properties, as in Table 1, the right hands sides of eqs. 8 and 9 depend on the difference in the effective Poisson's ratios between the crown and side sections, and hence an axial strain causes circumferential displacements in proportion to the difference. Likewise, it can be shown that the right hands sides of eqs. 11 and 12 depend primarily on the difference between inverse effective moduli, and hence an internal pressure causes the circumferential displacement in proportion to that difference. Stated differently, for the axial strain condition only Case 2 in Table 1 leads to non-zero circumferential displacements, while for the internal pressure condition, only Case 1 leads to nontrivial circumferential displacements.

FINITE-LENGTH CYLINDER

The Kantorovich technique [5] is used to study a cylinder of finite length. The approximations to the displacements are motivated by the results for the infinite cylinder. As such, using the quarter symmetry of the problem, it is assumed that

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, s) &= u_o(x) + u_1(x) \cos(2s) \\ v(x, s) &= v_1(x) \sin(2s) \\ w(x, s) &= w_o(x) + w_1(x) \cos(2s) \\ \Psi_x(x, s) &= \Psi_{x_0}(x) + \Psi_{x_1}(x) \cos(2s) \\ \Psi_s(x, s) &= \Psi_{s_1}(x) \sin(2s) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Whereas the infinite-length cylinder has a radial displacement that is independent of s and a circumferential displacement that is linear in s , with the rotations being zero and the axial displacement being linear in x and independent of s , the approximations of eq. 13 assume the deformations vary harmonically in s and are to-be-determined functions of x . These assumed forms are chosen strictly for convenience and ignore the fact that a number of the variables have discontinuous first derivatives with respect to s at s^* .

The total potential energy of the cylinder, for either loading condition, is given by

$$\Pi = \iint_{x s} (N_x \epsilon_x + N_s \epsilon_s + N_{xs} \gamma_{xs} + Q_x \gamma_{rx} + Q_s \gamma_{rs} + M_x \kappa_x + M_s \kappa_s + M_{xs} \kappa_{xs} - q_o w) ds dx \quad (14)$$

Substituting in the approximate deformations, eq. 13, integrating explicitly with respect to s , and taking the first variation of the resulting expression leads to the governing equations for the variables $u_o(x) \dots \psi_{s_1}(x)$. These governing equations consist of eight ordinary constant coefficient differential equations of second order. The equations are of the form

$$[C_2] \{y''(x)\} + [C_1] \{y'(x)\} + [C_o] \{y(x)\} = \{Q\}, \quad (15)$$

where

$$\{y(x)\}^T = \{u_o(x), u_1(x), v_1(x), w_o(x), w_1(x), \psi_{x_o}(x), \psi_{x_1}(x), \psi_{s_1}(x)\} \quad (16)$$

and

$$\{Q\}^T = \{0, 0, 0, q_o, 0, 0, 0, 0\}. \quad (17)$$

The matrices $[C_2]$, $[C_1]$, and $[C_o]$ are functions of the material properties of the crown and side, and the radius R and s^* . The complete solution for each $y_i(x)$ consists of a homogeneous part and a particular part. The homogeneous parts result in a 16-th order characteristic equation with two repeated zero roots and 14 distinct complex roots. Thus the homogeneous solution for each $y_i(x)$ has terms of the form

$$(A + iB) e^{(\alpha + i\beta)x} \quad (18)$$

plus a constant plus a term linear in x , these last two terms representing the repeated zero root solutions. In the above A , B , α , and β are real numbers. The particular solution for each $y_i(x)$ is a constant. For the axial strain condition there is no particular solution.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

For numerical results the cases in Table 1 will continue to be specifically considered. Moreover, as experiments with segmented-stiffness cylinders will begin with small scale cylinders, a thickness corresponding to eight layers of graphite epoxy ($H = 0.0012\text{m}$) and a radius of 0.127m ($R = 0.127\text{m}$) will be used in the numerical results. Also, $\theta^* = \pi/6$ and for the axial strain condition $\bar{\epsilon}_x = -0.001$ will be used, while for the pressure loading condition $q_o = 0.102$ MPa (1 atmosphere) will be used.

Infinite-Length Cylinder: Exact Solution

To consider an infinite-length cylinder using the approximate solution of eq. 13, the functions of x are replaced by unknown constants. Considering the axial strain condition, and using the numerical values of material properties for Case 2 in both the exact (eqs. 7, 8, and 9) and approximate infinite-length solutions, fig. 3 results. In this figure the circumferential and radial displacements, normalized by cylinder wall thickness, are shown as a function of the normalized circumferential coordinate. As can be seen, the approximate solution smooths the circumferential displacement but provides an excellent prediction for the radial displacement. With the smoothing effect of the approximate displacement field in mind, attention now turns to the results for the approximate solution for the finite-length cylinder.

Fig. 3 - Comparison of exact and approximate infinite cylinder solutions, $\bar{\epsilon}_x = -0.001$

Finite-Length Cylinder: Approximate Solution

Consider now the axial strain condition for a finite-length cylinder with the material properties of Case 2 and $L/R = 2$. Solution of the eigenvalue problem and construction of the solution of the form given in eq. 18 leads to the results shown in figs. 4, 5, and 6. Figures 4a and b illustrate the overall variation of v and w with x and s . Figures 5a and b show details of v and w versus s at midspan, while figs. 6a and b show the characteristics of w and v versus x at specific s locations. Normalized quantities are used and the vertical axes are scaled to reflect the infinite length cylinder response as determined from the approximate solution of eq. 13 (with constants rather than functions of x) and as shown in fig. 3. Three interesting characteristics are immediately obvious from the figures. First, whereas with the infinitely-long cylinder w does not vary with s , for the finite-length cylinder, as can be seen in fig. 3b, there is a variation of w with s . Specifically, fig. 5b illustrates the variation of w with s at midspan, the results from the infinite-length cylinder approximate solution being shown for comparison. For the problem parameters used here, at midspan w is 1.5 times larger at the crown of the cylinder than at the sides. It is interesting that the ratio of the Poisson's ratios between the crown and side for Case 2 of Table 1 is 1.5. Second, when compared to the infinite-length solution, the value of v at midspan, fig. 5a, is greatly reduced. This is a reflection of the strong effect of the $v=0$ condition at the cylinder ends restraining the overall circumferential displacements. Third, as shown in figs. 6a and b, whereas the variation of w with x at all s locations is confined primarily to the cylinder ends, i.e., a boundary layer effect, the variation of v with x involves the entire cylinder length, i.e., there is no boundary layer for v . The absence of a boundary layer for the circumferential displacement can be traced the values of the eigenvalues in eq. 18. The eigenvalues and associated eigenvectors that characterize v have significantly different values than those that characterize w . Essentially, the St. Venant effect for v takes place over a different length scale than the St. Venant effect for w . A further discussion of the eigenvalue issue can be found in ref. 6. If Cases 1 and 3 are examined for the axial strain condition, the response is very much like that of a classical single-laminate cylinder, namely, there is very little circumferential displacement and the radial displacement is almost independent of s . This behavior is like the infinite-length case, where only the difference in Poisson's ratios were important in determining the response.

Fig. 4 - Approximate finite cylinder solutions for $L/R = 2$, $\bar{\epsilon}_x = -0.001$

Fig. 5 - Comparison of approximate infinite and finite cylinder solutions for $L/R = 2$ at midspan, $\bar{\epsilon}_x = -0.001$

Fig. 6 - Variation with x/L of approximate finite cylinder solutions for $L/R = 2$, $\bar{\epsilon}_x = -0.001$

If Case 1 of Table 1 and the internal pressure condition is considered, the counterpart to fig. 6 is shown in fig. 7. Figures 7a and b again illustrate the characteristics of w and v versus x at specific s locations. These are the same locations as in fig. 6, but notice that for the pressure loading case the greater radial displacement occurs at $s=\pi R/2$ instead of $s=0$. Furthermore, the sign of v is reversed. If Cases 2 and 3 are examined for the internal pressure condition, the response of the cylinder is very much like that of a single-laminate cylinder. Again, this behavior reflects the findings of the infinite-length case, where only the difference in effective extensional moduli were important.

CONCLUDING COMENTS

This paper has discussed the response of segmented-stiffness cylinders to simple loading conditions. Though the results shown suffer from the smoothing effect of the approximate solution technique, it is clear the response of such cylinders is unique. The details of the response near $s=s^*$ have not been discussed as the analysis technique was not suited for this level of analysis. It would be a logical next step to investigate the details of the response in that location. No doubt the response is sharper, like the infinite-length cylinder, leading to high stresses. With the segmented stiffness construction, differences in thermal expansion and a temperature change may also lead to interesting response. Additionally, there is the issue of buckling, post-buckling, and collapse as a result of increased axial compression. It would seem axially stiffer segments may react the majority of the axial load and buckle, thereby transferring the axial load to the less axially stiff segments. With a further increase in axial compression these segments will eventually buckle and the cylinder would collapse. Finally there is the issue of bending loads. This is a complicated problem, particularly when the segment in compression buckles. In short, this type of cylinder construction provides for considerable research into a number of areas.

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Fig. 7 - Variation with x/L of approximate finite cylinder solutions for $L/R = 2$, $q_0 = 1$ atm.

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